
Plan Overview

A Data Management Plan created using DMPonline

Title: SteeleLab PhD Data Management Plan

Creator: Gary Steele

Affiliation: Delft University of Technology

Template: TU Delft Data Management Plan template (2021)

Project abstract:

PhD research in the SteeleLab Research Group

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SteeleLab PhD Data Management Plan

0. Administrative questions

1. Name of data management support staff consulted during the preparation of this plan.

Esther Plomp, TNW Data Steward

2. Date of consultation with support staff.

1. Data description and collection or re-use of existing data

3. Provide a general description of the type of data you will be working with, including any re-used data:

Type of data	File format(s)	How will data be collected (for re-used data: source and terms of use)?	Purpose of processing	Storage location	Who will have access to the data
Measurement Data Files	.dat, maybe hdf5 in future, time-stamped folders	automated collection by measurement scripts or simulation code	perform physics experiments	local measurement computers, synced to SteeleLab synology nas, nightly backups to databases stored on bulk drives	all SteeleLab members, external collaborators on a case-by-case basis if needed
Cleanroom images	png, tif, etc	copying from instruments in CR to folder synced to our NAS	diagnosis and documentation of fabrication process	NAS will sync from U: drive, then goes into nightly backups	all SteeleLab members, external collaborators on a case-by-case basis if needed
Code	python, other languages	git repositories in SteeleLab group in gitlab.tudelft.nl	generation of measurements, analysis of data files, generation of chip designs, simulations of devices	gitlab.tudelft.nl	all SteeleLab members, external collaborators on a case-by-case basis if needed

4. How much data storage will you require during the project lifetime?

- 250 GB - 5 TB

II. Documentation and data quality

5. What documentation will accompany data?

- Methodology of data collection
- README file or other documentation explaining how data is organised
- Data dictionary explaining the variables used
- Data will be deposited in a data repository at the end of the project (see section V) and data discoverability and re-usability will be ensured by adhering to the repository's metadata standards
- Documentation in an Electronic Lab Notebook

CR images: metadata in format of timestamps, image metadata, folder hierarchy

Measurement data files: timestamps, folder hierarchy, each dataset is in a timestamped folder accompanied by a copy of the measurement script and also a git hash indicating library versions of our measurement code library

Electronic lab notebooks: level 0 documentation via logbook generator

(<https://gitlab.tudelft.nl/steelelab/logbook-generator>), periodic "level 1" jupyter notebooks (weekly or biweekly or monthly) logbooks indicating measurement plan and summarising results, "level 2" notebooks collecting results into thematic structure, "level 3" notebooks accompanying papers / chapters generating PDFs of figures

Data from thesis and publications will be released as a minimum "level 0" in our QN / TNW taxonomy (https://zenodo.org/record/2556949#.YaeFU_HMK3A), with strong emphasis on "level 1" compliance (currently the norm in the group).

No attempt will be made to create a "standardized metadata structure" as our experimental protocols vary on nearly a daily basis, and therefore instead full metadata disclosure will be provided by the measurement script, along with metadata describing the axis labels, such as the "meta.txt" standard (<https://nswb.tn.tudelft.nl/~gsteele/spyview/#meta>) or similar.

III. Storage and backup during research process

6. Where will the data (and code, if applicable) be stored and backed-up during the project lifetime?

- Another storage system - please explain below, including provided security measures

Every piece of generated is synced immediately to the SteeleLab NAS server (<https://nas-steelelab.tnw.tudelft.nl/>). The server runs synology with regular updates. The sync is achieved via Synology Drive. The data is the backed up nightly via Hyperbackup to the TU Delft bulk storage, which

in turn is replicated on two location and provides also backups of the backup databases.
Code is stored on the TU Delft gitlab.

IV. Legal and ethical requirements, codes of conduct

7. Does your research involve human subjects or 3rd party datasets collected from human participants?

- No

8A. Will you work with personal data? (information about an identified or identifiable natural person)

If you are not sure which option to select, ask your [Faculty Data Steward](#) for advice. You can also check with the [privacy website](#) or contact the privacy team: privacy-tud@tudelft.nl

- No

8B. Will you work with any types of confidential or classified data or code as listed below? (tick all that apply)

If you are not sure which option to select, ask your [Faculty Data Steward](#) for advice.

- No, I will not work with any confidential or classified data/code

9. How will ownership of the data and intellectual property rights to the data be managed?

For projects involving commercially-sensitive research or research involving third parties, seek advice of your [Faculty Contract Manager](#) when answering this question. If this is not the case, you can use the example below.

The default group policy is that all work done in the SteeleLab will be openly shared in the public domain.

Should involved parties identify a possible commercial application that could be worth protecting as intellectual property, this will be signalled by said parties before the work enters the public domain and a discussion about the possibilities for protecting said intellectual property will be discussed with the involved partners and the faculty contract manager.

V. Data sharing and long-term preservation

26. What data will be publicly shared?

- All data (and code) underlying published articles / reports / theses

Level 0 compliance as minimum, Level 1 compliance as the norm (see QN policy for taxonomy).

28. How will you share your research data (and code)?

- I will upload the data to another data repository (please provide details below)

Our preference is Zenodo due to web interface and ease of use.

30. How much of your data will be shared in a research data repository?

- 100 GB - 1 TB

31. When will the data (or code) be shared?

- As soon as corresponding results (papers, theses, reports) are published

32. Under what licence will be the data/code released?

- CC BY
- MIT License
- GPL 3.0+

Data will be released under CC-BY and code, by default, under the MIT licence or GPL under consultation with the authors.

VI. Data management responsibilities and resources

33. Is TU Delft the lead institution for this project?

- Yes, leading the collaboration

34. If you leave TU Delft (or are unavailable), who is going to be responsible for the data resulting from this project?

I presume the TNW Data Steward (to be determined, waiting on feedback from Esther).

Note that all group members have access to all data by default.

The one open question is the admin password of the NAS server: currently, only I have that information. The backups are not encrypted. SSH access would need to be secured to the server rsbt-qn in order to restore the data from backup files, but this can be achieved via ICT support should the need arise as rsbt-qn is a faculty managed server.

35. What resources (for example financial and time) will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable)?

Zenodo does not yet have any limits relevant for us as far as i know.